

QCMC-Based Quantum Markov Blanket Discovery for Semantic Quantum Networks

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Abstract—Quantum semantic communication may benefit from identifying which parts of a multipartite quantum environment are conditionally relevant to a target subsystem. We formulate this task as finite-size Quantum Markov Blanket discovery using quantum conditional mutual information (QCMC). A deterministic greedy algorithm selects the remaining subsystem with the largest conditional contribution and is compared with a static baseline based on pairwise quantum mutual information. The evaluation uses exact density-matrix simulation over 112 benchmark conditions spanning Markov-star, redundant two-branch, and Greenberger–Horne–Zeilinger states, four noise levels, and four QCMC thresholds. In noiseless Markov-star states, the greedy method retains one candidate and excludes 66.7% to 85.7% of the candidate set. In the noiseless redundant two-branch state, it identifies the two-subsystem reference blanket, whereas the static baseline retains all four candidates. Across all conditions, the greedy blanket is smaller in 7 cases, equal in 105, and never larger. The Greenberger–Horne–Zeilinger (GHZ) negative control retains every candidate, showing that compactness depends on the correlation structure. The reported reductions concern candidate subsystems and do not directly imply lower transmitted-qubit or channel-use requirements.

Index Terms—Quantum Markov blankets, quantum conditional mutual information, conditional independence, subsystem selection, quantum semantic communication.

I. INTRODUCTION

Future quantum networks will support distributed communication and computation using quantum states, entanglement, and networked quantum devices [1]. Their operation is constrained by noisy channels, fragile quantum memories, and the cost of preparing and processing multipartite states. Semantic communication addresses a related problem in classical networks by prioritising information that is relevant to a task rather than reproducing every source symbol [2]. Recent work has begun to combine semantic processing with quantum communication [3]. This motivates a basic selection question: given a multipartite state and a target subsystem, which surrounding subsystems remain relevant after conditioning on those already selected?

Classical Markov blankets formalise conditional relevance in probabilistic graphical models [4]. We extend this idea to a finite quantum candidate set by calling Q an ϵ -Quantum Markov Blanket (QMB) of target A when $I(A : R | Q)_\rho \leq \epsilon$, where $R = \mathcal{B} \setminus Q$. Zero QCMC gives an exact quantum Markov structure, while small QCMC supports approximate recovery of the joint state from ρ_{AQ} through a channel acting on Q [5], [6]. This information-theoretic interpretation neither

requires R to be classical nor directly establishes a reduction in communication resources.

We formulate minimum-cardinality finite-size QMB discovery and evaluate a deterministic greedy method that repeatedly selects the candidate maximising $I(A : B_i | Q)_\rho$. A static baseline ranks candidates once using $I(A : B_i)_\rho$. Exact density-matrix experiments cover 112 conditions across Markov-star, redundant two-branch, and GHZ states. Greedy discovery recovers the compact reference blankets in the noiseless structured cases, is never larger than the static blanket over the tested conditions, and retains every candidate for the GHZ negative control. The contributions are a QCMC-based finite-size formulation, deterministic discovery and cost accounting, and a controlled study of compactness, noise sensitivity, conditional redundancy, and negative controls. Reported gains concern candidate-subsystem reduction.

II. QUANTUM MARKOV BLANKETS AND DISCOVERY

A. Finite-Size Quantum Markov Blankets

Let A denote the target quantum subsystem and let $\mathcal{B} = \{B_1, \dots, B_m\}$ denote the set of candidate environment subsystems. For a selected subset $Q \subseteq \mathcal{B}$, define the residual environment as $R = \mathcal{B} \setminus Q$. The symbols Q and R denote both sets of subsystem labels and their corresponding composite quantum subsystems.

All logarithms are base two. The von Neumann entropy of subsystem X is

$$S(X)_\rho = -\text{Tr}(\rho_X \log_2 \rho_X). \quad (1)$$

The conditional dependence remaining between A and R , once Q is available, is measured by the quantum conditional mutual information (QCMC)

$$I(A : R | Q)_\rho = S(AQ)_\rho + S(QR)_\rho - S(Q)_\rho - S(AQR)_\rho. \quad (2)$$

Strong subadditivity ensures that $I(A : R | Q)_\rho \geq 0$. Equality, $I(A : R | Q)_\rho = 0$, characterises an exact quantum Markov chain $A \leftrightarrow Q \leftrightarrow R$. In this case, there exists a completely positive trace-preserving recovery map $\mathcal{R}_{Q \rightarrow QR}$ such that

$$\rho_{AQR} = (\text{id}_A \otimes \mathcal{R}_{Q \rightarrow QR})(\rho_{AQ}). \quad (3)$$

This exact recovery property follows from the structure of states that saturate strong subadditivity [5].

For finite systems, exact conditional independence is generally too restrictive. We therefore call Q an ϵ -QMB for A when

$$I(A : R | Q)_\rho \leq \epsilon, \quad R = \mathcal{B} \setminus Q. \quad (4)$$

For every state, there exists a recovery map acting on Q for which

$$F(\rho_{AQR}, (\text{id}_A \otimes \mathcal{R}_{Q \rightarrow QR})(\rho_{AQ})) \geq 2^{-\frac{1}{2}I(A:R|Q)_\rho}, \quad (5)$$

where the root fidelity is

$$F(\rho, \sigma) = \|\sqrt{\rho}\sqrt{\sigma}\|_1. \quad (6)$$

The bound approaches one as the QCMDI approaches zero [6]. Small QCMDI therefore does not imply that ρ_{AQR} is a product state. Rather, it implies that the joint state can be approximately recovered from ρ_{AQ} by a channel acting on Q .

The minimum-cardinality finite-size problem is

$$Q_\epsilon^* \in \arg \min_{Q \subseteq \mathcal{B}} |Q| \quad \text{subject to} \quad I(A : \mathcal{B} \setminus Q | Q)_\rho \leq \epsilon. \quad (7)$$

A feasible solution always exists because $Q = \mathcal{B}$ leaves an empty residual, for which $I(A : \emptyset | Q)_\rho = 0$. The relevant question is whether a proper subset of \mathcal{B} satisfies (4). Compactness is therefore state dependent and is not assumed to hold for every multipartite state.

B. Greedy QCMDI Discovery

An exhaustive solution of (7) may require evaluating up to 2^m candidate subsets. We therefore use deterministic forward selection. At iteration t , let Q_t denote the selected blanket and let $R_t = \mathcal{B} \setminus Q_t$ denote the remaining candidates.

For each candidate $B_i \in R_t$, define the conditional information gain as

$$g_i^{(t)} = I(A : B_i | Q_t)_\rho. \quad (8)$$

For any $B_i \in R_t$, the QCMDI chain rule gives

$$I(A : R_t | Q_t)_\rho = I(A : B_i | Q_t)_\rho + I(A : R_t \setminus \{B_i\} | Q_t B_i)_\rho. \quad (9)$$

The second term in (9) is the residual QCMDI after B_i is added to the blanket. Selecting the candidate with the largest $g_i^{(t)}$ therefore gives the largest one-step reduction in residual QCMDI.

Algorithm 1 begins with $Q = \emptyset$. It stops when the residual QCMDI is no larger than ϵ , when no candidate remains, or when the maximum blanket size q_{\max} is reached. Candidate-score ties within tolerance τ are resolved by selecting the smallest subsystem index.

The algorithm returns an ϵ -QMB when $\Delta \leq \epsilon$. If it stops because $R = \emptyset$, the result is feasible but provides no candidate reduction. If it stops at q_{\max} while $\Delta > \epsilon$, the requested threshold has not been met. Because the procedure is greedy, it does not guarantee the globally smallest solution of (7).

Algorithm 1 Deterministic greedy QCMDI discovery

Require: State $\rho_{AB_1 \dots B_m}$, candidate set $\mathcal{B} = \{B_1, \dots, B_m\}$, threshold ϵ , maximum size q_{\max} , tolerance τ

Ensure: Selected blanket Q , residual set R

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1:  $Q \leftarrow \emptyset$ 
2:  $R \leftarrow \mathcal{B}$ 
3: loop
4:    $\Delta \leftarrow I(A : R | Q)_\rho$ 
5:   if  $\Delta \leq \epsilon$  or  $R = \emptyset$  or  $|Q| = q_{\max}$  then
6:     break
7:   end if
8:   for all  $B_i \in R$  do
9:      $g_i \leftarrow I(A : B_i | Q)_\rho$ 
10:  end for
11:   $g_{\max} \leftarrow \max_{B_i \in R} g_i$ 
12:   $i^* \leftarrow \min\{i : B_i \in R, |g_i - g_{\max}| \leq \tau\}$ 
13:   $Q \leftarrow Q \cup \{B_{i^*}\}$ 
14:   $R \leftarrow R \setminus \{B_{i^*}\}$ 
15: end loop
16: return  $Q, R, \Delta$ 

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C. Static-QCMDI Baseline and Evaluation Cost

We compare greedy QCMDI discovery with a static pairwise-QCMDI ranking baseline. For each candidate B_i , the baseline computes

$$I(A : B_i)_\rho = S(A)_\rho + S(B_i)_\rho - S(AB_i)_\rho. \quad (10)$$

The candidates are ranked once in descending order of $I(A : B_i)_\rho$ and then added to Q in that fixed order. After each addition, the baseline evaluates the same stopping condition $I(A : R | Q)_\rho \leq \epsilon$. Ties are resolved by selecting the candidate with the lowest index. Unlike greedy QCMDI discovery, the static ranking is not updated after conditioning on the selected subsystems and may therefore retain candidates whose pairwise relevance becomes redundant given the current blanket.

For m candidates and a final blanket of size k , the greedy method evaluates the conditional score of every remaining candidate at each selection step. Under the counting convention used here, the total number of QCMDI evaluations is

$$N_{\text{greedy}}^{\text{QCMDI}}(m, k) = \sum_{j=0}^{k-1} (m-j) + (k+1) = \frac{k(2m-k+1)}{2} + k + 1. \quad (11)$$

The summation counts the candidate-score evaluations. The term $k+1$ counts the residual-QCMDI tests performed once before the first selection and once after each of the k selections.

When all candidates are retained, $k = m$, and (11) reduces to

$$N_{\text{greedy}}^{\text{QCMDI}}(m, m) = \frac{(m+1)(m+2)}{2}. \quad (12)$$

The static baseline computes m pairwise QMI values once and performs $k+1$ residual-QCMDI evaluations. Its search cost is therefore reported as

$$N_{\text{static}}^{\text{QMI}}(m) = m, \quad N_{\text{static}}^{\text{QCMDI}}(k) = k + 1. \quad (13)$$

QMI and QCMDI evaluations are reported separately because they do not have identical computational costs. These counts

TABLE I
BENCHMARK-STATE PARTITIONS

Family	n	Target	Candidates	Reference Q
Markov-star	4, 6, 8	$\{0\}$	$\{B_1, \dots, B_{n-1}\}$	$\{B_1\}$
Redundant two-branch	6	$\{0, 1\}$	$\{B_2, B_3, B_4, B_5\}$	$\{B_2, B_3\}$
GHZ	4, 6, 8	$\{0\}$	$\{B_1, \dots, B_{n-1}\}$	None

measure search-level overhead under the stated implementation and do not include state preparation, reduced-state construction, or possible reuse of previously computed entropies. Wall-clock time additionally depends on the processor, numerical libraries, and an eigensolver. Exact QMI and QCMDI evaluation requires reduced density matrices and von Neumann entropies. For general n -qubit states, the underlying matrix dimensions grow exponentially with n , limiting exact density-matrix simulation to modest system sizes. Larger systems would therefore require structured-state methods, approximate entropy or QCMDI estimators, or variational surrogates.

III. FINITE-SIZE EVALUATION

A. Experimental Protocol

We evaluated the greedy QCMDI method and the static-QMI baseline using exact density-matrix simulation in Python and NumPy. The target subsystem is denoted by A , the candidate environment by \mathcal{B} , the selected blanket by Q , and the residual environment by $R = \mathcal{B} \setminus Q$.

The benchmark suite contains three state families. Qubits are indexed from zero. For the Markov-star and GHZ families, the target A is qubit 0 and the candidate set is $\mathcal{B} = \{B_1, \dots, B_{n-1}\}$. For the six-qubit redundant two-branch family, the target is $A = A_0A_1 = \{0, 1\}$ and the candidate set is $\mathcal{B} = \{B_2, B_3, B_4, B_5\}$. Table I summarises the tested partitions and reference blankets.

For $u \in [0, 1]$, let $p_u(1) = u$, $p_u(0) = 1 - u$. The benchmark parameters are $\alpha = 0.1958760119$, $\beta = 0.0860154938$, $r = 0.23$, $\delta_4 = 0.02$, and $\delta_5 = 0.05$.

a) *Markov-star family*: Let $\mathbf{z} = (z_2, \dots, z_{n-1})$ and $p_r(\mathbf{z}) = \prod_{j=2}^{n-1} p_r(z_j)$, where $x \in 0, 1$ and $\mathbf{z} \in 0, 1^{n-2}$. The noiseless Markov-star state is

$$\rho_{\text{MS}}^{(n)} = \sum_{x, \mathbf{z}} p_\alpha(x) p_r(\mathbf{z}) \times |x, x, \mathbf{z}\rangle \langle x, x, \mathbf{z}|. \quad (14)$$

Thus, A and B_1 contain the same classical bit, whereas B_2, \dots, B_{n-1} are independent of it. Consequently,

$$I(A : B_2 \cdots B_{n-1} | B_1)_{\rho_{\text{MS}}^{(n)}} = 0, \quad (15)$$

and the noiseless reference blanket is $Q_{\text{ref}} = \{B_1\}$.

b) *Redundant two-branch family*: With subsystem ordering $(A_0, A_1, B_2, B_3, B_4, B_5)$, the noiseless six-qubit state is

$$\begin{aligned} \rho_{\text{RTB}} = & \sum_{x, y, e_4, e_5} p_\alpha(x) p_\beta(y) p_{\delta_4}(e_4) p_{\delta_5}(e_5) \\ & \times |x, y, x, y, x \oplus e_4, x \oplus e_5\rangle \\ & \times \langle x, y, x, y, x \oplus e_4, x \oplus e_5| \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

Here B_2 carries X , B_3 carries Y , and B_4 and B_5 are noisy copies of information already available in B_2 . Hence,

$$I(A : B_4B_5 | B_2B_3)_{\rho_{\text{RTB}}} = 0. \quad (17)$$

The parameters yield $I(A : B_2)_\rho > I(A : B_4)_\rho > I(A : B_5)_\rho > I(A : B_3)_\rho$, so the static ranking selects the two redundant candidates before B_3 .

c) *GHZ negative control*: For $n \in \{4, 6, 8\}$,

$$|\text{GHZ}_n\rangle = \frac{|0\rangle^{\otimes n} + |1\rangle^{\otimes n}}{\sqrt{2}}. \quad (18)$$

These synthetic states isolate conditional-relevance structure and do not constitute an end-to-end semantic-communication task.

Each benchmark state ρ was subjected to global depolarising noise,

$$\rho_p = (1 - p)\rho + p \frac{\mathbb{I}_{2^n}}{2^n} \quad (19)$$

where $p \in \{0, 0.05, 0.10, 0.20\}$. The QCMDI stopping threshold was varied over $\epsilon \in \{10^{-6}, 10^{-3}, 10^{-2}, 0.05\}$.

The protocol comprises 48 Markov-star, 16 redundant two-branch, and 48 GHZ conditions, for a total of 112 state-noise-threshold combinations. Each condition was evaluated using both methods, producing 224 result rows. No separate blanket-size cap was imposed, so $q_{\text{max}} = m$. The numerical tolerance was $\tau = 10^{-12}$, and candidate-score ties within this tolerance were resolved by selecting the lowest subsystem index. Wall-clock selection time was measured three times per condition and summarised by the median.

For $m = |\mathcal{B}|$ candidates, the retained candidate fraction is

$$r_Q = \frac{|Q|}{m} \quad (20)$$

and the candidate-subsystem reduction, reported as a percentage, is

$$G_Q = 100(1 - r_Q). \quad (21)$$

This metric measures the percentage of candidate subsystems excluded from Q . It does not directly measure transmitted physical qubits, entangled pairs, channel uses, latency, or energy.

We also report the final residual dependence

$$\Delta_Q = I(A : R | Q)_\rho, \quad (22)$$

and, when $I(A : \mathcal{B})_\rho > 0$, the retained-dependence fraction

$$\eta_Q = \frac{I(A : Q)_\rho}{I(A : \mathcal{B})_\rho}. \quad (23)$$

Algorithmic overhead is reported using QMI and QCMDI evaluation counts. Wall-clock time is treated as a secondary, platform-dependent measurement.

B. Compactness and Noise Sensitivity

Figure 1 shows the candidate-subsystem reduction obtained by greedy QCMDI discovery. For noiseless Markov-star states, both methods identify the single reference candidate. The selected blanket contains 1 of 3, 1 of 5, and 1 of 7 candidates for $n = 4$, $n = 6$, and $n = 8$, giving reductions of 66.7%, 80.0%, and 85.7%, respectively.

Noise makes the choice of ϵ consequential. At the strict thresholds 10^{-6} and 10^{-3} , noisy Markov-star states generally require all candidates to be retained. At $\epsilon = 0.05$, compact

blankets remain available. For $n = 4$, the reduction is 66.7% at all nonzero noise levels. For $n = 6$, the reductions are 80.0%, 80.0%, and 60.0% for $p = 0.05$, $p = 0.10$, and $p = 0.20$, respectively. For $n = 8$, the corresponding reductions are 85.7%, 85.7%, and 57.1%.

Across all pruned Markov-star conditions, the retained-dependence fraction satisfies $\eta_Q \geq 0.9123$, with median 0.9884. Thus, the observed compactness preserves most of the target–environment dependence, although the attainable reduction depends on both the noise level and the stopping threshold.

C. Baseline Comparison and Negative Control

The redundant two-branch state distinguishes conditional relevance from a fixed pairwise ranking. In the noiseless case, greedy QCMDI discovery selects $Q = \{B_2, B_3\}$, which matches the reference blanket and retains 2 of 4 candidates. The static-QMDI baseline uses the fixed order (B_2, B_4, B_5, B_3) and retains all four candidates before meeting the residual-QCMDI condition. The additional candidates B_4 and B_5 are pairwise informative but become redundant after conditioning on the selected blanket.

Across the 16 redundant-state conditions, the greedy blanket is smaller in 7 cases, equal in 9, and never larger. At $\epsilon = 0.05$, greedy discovery retains 2, 3, and 3 of the 4 candidates for $p = 0.05$, $p = 0.10$, and $p = 0.20$, respectively, whereas the static baseline retains all four. Among the pruned redundant-state conditions, the minimum retained-dependence fraction is 0.9592.

Across all 112 benchmark conditions, the greedy blanket is smaller in 7 cases, equal in 105, and never larger than the static-QMDI blanket. For every tested GHZ condition, both methods exhaust the residual set and retain all candidates, giving 0% candidate reduction. This negative control shows that compactness depends on the state, partition, and tolerance and is not guaranteed by the discovery procedure.

D. Discovery Overhead

Figure 2 summarises the discovery cost. For an eight-qubit Markov-star state that stops after one selection, greedy discovery requires 9 QCMDI evaluations. The static baseline requires 7 QMDI evaluations and 2 residual-QCMDI evaluations.

In an eight-qubit full-retention case, greedy discovery requires 36 QCMDI evaluations, whereas the static baseline requires 7 QMDI evaluations and 8 QCMDI evaluations. Greedy discovery, therefore, applies a stronger conditional selection rule but incurs a higher worst-case evaluation cost.

The wall-clock measurements follow the same trend, although their absolute values depend on the processor, software environment, and eigensolver. Evaluation counts, therefore, provide the primary overhead comparison.

E. Numerical Consistency

Every solution with a nonempty residual satisfies $\Delta_Q \leq \epsilon$ within the numerical tolerance 10^{-12} . When $R = \emptyset$, the

QCMDI condition is satisfied trivially, but no candidate reduction remains. The maximum absolute error in the QCMDI chain-rule identity over all 224 result rows is 8.88×10^{-16} , consistent with floating-point precision.

All numerical results and figures were produced from the same simulation outputs using the fixed parameter settings reported in this section.

IV. DISCUSSION AND LIMITATIONS

The experiments show that compact QMBs arise when the state contains conditional redundancy. Greedy QCMDI discovery removes candidates whose pairwise relevance becomes redundant after conditioning, whereas no candidate reduction is obtained for the tested GHZ states. Blanket size is therefore determined jointly by the state, subsystem partition, noise level, and tolerance ϵ . A smaller ϵ enforces stricter residual conditional independence and generally retains more candidates under noise. The retained-dependence fraction η_Q is an information-theoretic diagnostic and should not be interpreted as semantic fidelity, reconstruction accuracy, or task performance.

The reported reduction G_Q counts candidate subsystems excluded from the blanket. It does not directly measure transmitted qubits, channel uses, entanglement consumption, latency, energy, or error-correction cost. Such claims require an end-to-end protocol with a specified encoder, channel, receiver, and task-level metric. The evaluation is also limited to synthetic finite-size states and global depolarising noise. Exact density-matrix simulation scales exponentially and the reported search counts exclude state preparation, tomography, and hardware-level QCMDI estimation; larger systems will require structured-state methods or approximate estimators.

The greedy procedure is deterministic but not globally optimal, and the static-QMDI comparator does not represent all quantum feature-selection or graphical-model methods. The study further assumes a fixed state and candidate partition and does not address dynamic adaptation. Finally, $I(A : R | Q)_\rho \leq \epsilon$ does not imply that R is classical, separable, or uncorrelated, and it provides no confidentiality or cryptographic guarantee.

V. CONCLUSION

This work formulated Quantum Markov Blanket discovery as a finite-size conditional-independence problem and evaluated a deterministic greedy QCMDI method against a static-QMDI baseline. The results show that compact blankets can be identified when the underlying correlation structure contains conditional redundancy. In the Markov-star and redundant two-branch states, the greedy method selected blankets that were never larger than those of the baseline and, in several conditions, were smaller. The GHZ negative control retained all candidates, confirming that compactness is state-dependent rather than guaranteed by the algorithm.

The study also showed that blanket size depends strongly on the QCMDI threshold and noise level. At the same time, greedy conditional selection incurs a higher worst-case evaluation cost than static pairwise ranking. These findings establish QMB discovery as a deterministic finite-size method for correlation

Fig. 1. Candidate-subsystem reduction obtained by greedy QCMi discovery. All panels use the same 0–100% scale. Markov-star states admit compact blankets under suitable thresholds, whereas stricter thresholds and stronger noise reduce the amount of pruning. For the redundant two-branch state, the static-QMI baseline gives 0% reduction in every tested condition.

Fig. 2. Discovery overhead as the number of simulated qubits increases. Top: median wall-clock selection time on a logarithmic scale. Bottom: maximum QMI and QCMi evaluation counts under the stated counting convention. The counts are platform-independent under the stated counting convention, whereas wall-clock time is platform-dependent.

screening and candidate selection. Future work will determine whether this compactness translates into lower communication cost or improved task performance by evaluating end-to-end semantic communication protocols with explicit encoding,

channel, decoding and application-level metrics.

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